

Cupric Complexes of some Ortho-Hydroxy-Azo Dyes: Part II.

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This paper deals with the study of the cupric complexes of some substituted ortho-hydroxy-azo dyes, viz., 6-hydroxy-azo-benzene-3-methyl-2'-nitro-4'-sulphonic acid (abbreviated to 3-methyl-2'-nitro-4'-sulpho dye), 2,3-dimethyl-4'-sulpho dye, 2'-chloro-3-methyl-4'-sulpho dye and 3-methyl-4'-sulpho dye.

This investigation has been carried out to study the effects of various groups (viz., NO_2 , CH_3 and Cl) on the pK_a values of the ligands and the stability constants of their cupric complexes.

The pK_a values of the ligands are 8.75, 9.15, 8.81 and 8.75, respectively. The $\log K_1$ values of the cupric complexes are found to be 6.14, 6.21, 6.15 and 6.14 and those of $\log K_2$ are 4.64, 4.84, 4.67 and 4.61, respectively.

Ortho-hydroxy-azo dyes act as bidentates. Cupric ion is known to form coloured chelates with azo dyes. The previous work¹ on the nature of the cupric complexes of ortho-hydroxy-azo dyes has been extended by synthesising some more substituted azo dyes. The synthesis of these ligands enables us to study the effects of the groups in the 2' position (ring bearing $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group) on the pK_a values of the ligands and on the stability constants of their cupric complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ligands studied have all been synthesised. Freshly distilled *p*-cresol (B.D.H.) and an appropriate amine, after diazotisation, were coupled in alkaline medium. 2-Nitroaniline-4-sulphonic acid was prepared from acetanilide by Nietzki and Lerch's method² with some modifications.

2-Methylaniline-4-sulphonic acid and 2-chloroaniline-4-sulphonic acid were prepared by the sulphonation of freshly distilled *o*-toluidine (Riedel) and purified *o*-chloroaniline (Riedel) by the "baking process"³.

Sulphanilic acid used was of A.R. grade. The synthesised ligands were purified by the usual procedure¹ and were analysed for their nitrogen chlorine and sulphur contents. The results of analysis are given in Table I.

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TABLE I

Dye	% nitrogen		% sulphur		% chlorine	
	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
3-Methyl-2'-nitro-4'-sulpho dye	11.67	11.70	8.84	8.91	—	—
2',3-Dimethyl-4'-sulpho dye	8.55	8.54	9.72	9.76	—	—
2'-Chloro-3-methyl-4'-sulpho dye	7.97	8.03	9.11	9.15	10.14	10.19
3-Methyl-4'-sulpho dye	8.90	8.92	10.11	10.19	—	—

Composition of the cupric complexes was determined conductometrically by (i) the method of continuous variations and (ii) the monovariation method with $M/500$, $M/600$ and $M/800$ solutions. The highest complex formed was ML_2 . This composition was finally confirmed by spectrophotometric studies using Job's method of continuous variations with $M/10,000$ solution at two wave-lengths such that ΔA , i.e., the difference between the absorbance of the ligand and the mixture, was appreciable at the adjusted pH . The pH was 9.5, and the wave-lengths used were 360 $m\mu$ and 440 $m\mu$, 440 $m\mu$ and 460 $m\mu$, 420 $m\mu$ and 440 $m\mu$, and 360 $m\mu$ and 430 $m\mu$, respectively. Instruments used were Philips G-M-4144 conductivity bridge, Beckmann pH -meter and Carl Zeiss spectrophotometer.

The pK_a values of the ligands and the stability constants of their cupric complexes were determined by the procedure already described in our previous communication¹. The results obtained are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Dye	pK_a	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
3-Methyl-2'-nitro-4'-sulpho dye	8.75	6.14	4.64	10.78
2',3-Dimethyl-4'-sulpho dye	9.15	6.21	4.84	11.05
3-Methyl-2'-chloro-4'-sulpho dye	8.81	6.15	4.67	10.82
3-Methyl-4'-sulpho dye	8.75	6.14	4.61	10.75

DISCUSSION

From the above Table II, it is apparent that the nature and position of the group has a direct bearing on the pK_a value. But the effect is much less because substituents have been placed in the amine ring A and not in the ring B carrying the ortho-hydroxy group. Replacement of the ortho-hydrogen atom of the amine by a methyl group, which on a benzene ring acts as an electron donor⁴, increases the pK_a value from 8.75 to 9.15. Replacement of the same H by an electron acceptor nitro group should naturally decrease the pK_a value. But it is observed that there is almost no effect on the pK_a value (both being 8.75). A possible explanation for this unexpectedly higher pK_a value is that the ortho-nitro group may be involved in hydrogen bonding with the phenolic group, which is possible with the ortho-nitro group when the dye has a cis configuration: This may be stabilised by the hydrogen bonding.

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Chloro group differs from the aforesaid groups in that it is a σ -electron acceptor but a π -donor. π -effect is comparatively much more powerful and hence in most organic reactions chloro group is known to increase the electron density at the ortho and para-positions (*o-p*-directing influence on the electrophilic substitution). However, hydrogen does not form any double bond by π -donation or π -acceptance and this decreases the influence of π -effect on pK_a values. This explains the intermediate value of 8.81 of the 2'-chloro dye.

Correlating ligand basicity and complex stability, it is observed that a rough linear relationship between pK_a and $\log \beta_2$ does exist. Di-methyl dye with the highest pK_a (9.15) has the highest stability ($\log \beta_2$, 11.05). The pK_a value and the stability constants of the 2'-nitro dye should have been lowest because of the electron attracting character of the acidic nitro group. Actually it is found that the pK_a value is the same as that of the unsubstituted dye, while $\log \beta_2$ is slightly higher [pK_a , 8.75 and $\log \beta_2$, 10.78 (NO_2), 10.75 (H), respectively]. As has already been stated it is probable because of the possibility of hydrogen bonding from *o*-nitro position. Stability constants and the pK_a value of 2'-chloro dye (pK_a , 8.81 and $\log \beta_2$, 10.82) lie in between those of the 2'-methyl and the 2'-nitro dyes.

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